

Marketing and Showcasing of Art Via Social Media Website Art Socials

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Abstract:- Art Socials is a social media website that avails artists of different kinds to showcase their art on the platform and build a community of artists empowering them to connect and collaborate despite geographical disadvantages. This platform will provide an opportunity for artists to create their profiles, share their artwork, get feedback from other artists and also a collaborate feature which will send requests for collaborations to their desired artist(s).

Keywords:- HTML, CSS, Javascript(JS), ReactJS, MongoDB, ExpressJS, NodeJS.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media is much helpful in advertisement of art and artwork and thus by extension popularize artists themselves. Social media is an attractive tool and a hybrid or a mash-up element that has enabled agencies and companies to speak to an individual or just speak to each other on social media without any impediment, which is kind of a non-conventional way [1]. Social media websites have given people the opportunity to make friends online and surf friends-lists of others as well as making their own profiles [2], in this way our site ArtSocials can provide artists with a platform, features to create their profiles and ability to collaborate with each other. It has also been discovered that people on an average use more social media websites than they use emails or any other platforms on the internet [3]. Global Web Index reports that, "As users become more passive over time and increasingly turn to people in the public eye or well-known organizations for interesting content, social media will increasingly become a broadcast channel" [4]. This paper will allow people to be familiar with the social media website ArtSocials, which can be used by artists from various parts of the country to showcase their art and artwork and build a community of artists regardless of where they reside. This site can empower artists in many ways including giving them a platform that can be used free of cost and still find a way to earn income from their artwork probably from getting recognised by bigger artists who can sign them, or by collaborating with other artists of the community and distributing their songs further via various distributing

websites or companies. Moreover, consuming reviews from other counterparts will further enhance artists' creative spirit and nurture and hone their skills. Positive and negative reviews are part and parcel of any social media, however, this may also teach artists to respect all kinds of feedback and review, allowing artists to build patience-a very important aspect of an artist's.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social media has now garnered an influential impact on the lives of people, agencies and companies have now started extra value-powerful advertising and marketing avenues the usage of the internet like social networking websites, blogs, e-mail advertising, web sites advertisements and far more [5]. And because of that many commercial enterprises have shifted to social media for advertising and marketing [6]. "When we refer to social media, applications such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn, Pinterest, and Instagram often come to mind. These applications are driven by user-generated content, and are highly influential in a myriad of settings, from purchasing/selling behaviors, entrepreneurship, political issues, to venture capitalism" [7]. Corporations engage in social media basically with the intention of obtaining feedback from stakeholders [8]. "A record label in the music industry is an entity that handles such things as distribution, marketing, and artist promotion of an artist's recorded album releases. Furthermore, the term 'record label' is derived from a company that puts its label on recorded music releases" [9]. "Altogether, the music industry contributed \$143 billion to the economy in 2016, and according to the International Federation of the Phonographic Industry (2016), independent labels made up 29.88% of the recording industry in 2017. Marketing through social media has become an important part of music industry business strategies, and more so for independent record labels" [10]. Even though social media is a brilliant marketing and advertising platform [11], [12], [13], studies suggest that small businesses and groups are not able to benefit from social media yet [14], [15]. Social media has the ability to develop bidirectional relationships between patrons and organizations and thus has grown to be a part of many businesses' marketing plans and appears efficient. A

marketing plan is a “specific plan that describes activities selected to achieve specific marketing objectives for that product, within a set period of time” (Macy et al., 2016, p. 107) [16].” An aspect of social media is that it is free to use for anyone with an internet connection but also allows small to large businesses to produce paid advertisements and market their products or brands and create awareness to the target consumers or market(s). “The free aspect of social media allows small businesses to connect to consumers, but paid advertising options are available that would create brand awareness to the target market” [15]. One benefit to social media platforms is the opportunity for businesses to obtain analytics on the way the user interacts with the platform. Analytics are defined as “the use of data collected from a web site and its visitors to assess and improve the effectiveness of the website” (Macy et al., 2016, p. 61) [16]. “Social media marketing is simply another tool that needs to have a strategy

behind it in order to work” [17], [18]. Social media is a tool that artists use to understand and grasp their fanbase [19]. Consequently, social media is used as a research tool to better understand the user base, for marketing and advertising [19]. According to Kamara (2018), “small business music artists have utilized social media as a marketing tool to promote and brand themselves on the Internet” [13]. Pikes (2015) *et al.*, asserted that “the use of social media gives more independence to small businesses and artists because an independent artist would be able to create a social media account, find an audience, and release music directly to that audience. By doing this and bypassing the need for a label, an artist maintains complete artistic control and freedom. Artists and businesses are able to use social media, whether free or with paid advertisements, to promote themselves, and by doing this they are able to retain complete freedom on how to conduct business” [19].

Theories	Citations	Frequency
Social Exchange Theory	Choi et al. (2015); Hu et al. (2015); Matook et al. (b); Turel (2015); Shi et al. (2014); Krasnova et al. (2010)	6
Network theory	Yan et al. (2015a); Zhang and Wang (2012); Gray et al. (2011)	3
Organization theory	Lundmark et al. (2016); Schlagwein and Hu (2016); Oestreicher-Singer and Zalmanson (2013)	3
Learning theory	Fang et al. (2013); Chen and Sharma (2015)	2
Uses and gratifications theory	Ali-Hassan et al. (2015); Chiu and Huang (2015)	2
Elaboration likelihood model Theory	Ma et al. (2013); Cheung et al. (2012)	2
Rational choice theory	Hu et al. (2015); Turel (2015)	2
Attribution theory	Zhao et al. (2016); Porter et al. (2013)	2
Dual process theory	Back et al. (2012); Tang et al. (2012)	2
Social capital theory	Cao et al. (2015); Lu et al. (2015)	2
Innovation diffusion Theory	Stanko (2016); Lee et al. (2015a)	2
IS success model	Burtch et al. (2016); Xu et al. (2014)	2
IS hedonic value	Burtch et al. (2016); Xu et al. (2014)	2
Social penetration theory	Burtch et al. (2016); Xu et al. (2014)	2
Social comparison theory	Krasnova et al. (2015); Yan et al. (2015a)	2
Theory of planned behaviour	Zhao et al. (2016); Xie and Lee (2015)	2
Goal-setting Theory	Goes et al. (2016); Khansa et al. (2015)	2

Fig 1. Table shows the theories that are used in social mediaresearches.

Fig 2. Chart showing social media advertising value.

III. WORKFLOW & METHODOLOGY

The workflow is divided into two parts:

A. Frontend:

The structuring and scripting of the website is done through HTML, and CSS used for styling along with Bootstrap toolkit, for quick customization and responsiveness of the website. JQuery, a library of JS, is used for client side handling/modification of the webpage. For routing and API, ExpressJS is used.

B. Backend:

NodeJS, an open-source Javascript framework, is used for real-time web applications by employing push technology over websockets which makes the website seamless and smooth and allows users to optimally reuse the developer resources. NodeJS is used so that our website remains lightweight in the heat of real intensive real-time data applications running beyond various distributed devices. For the database, mongoDB using the Mongoose library, is incorporated to store the user data i.e, user credentials, passwords, usernames, pictures, videos, texts, profile etc., which is locally stored currently. For user registration and authentication PassportJS, a local mongoose plugin which is extensively used for handling authentication services, is incorporated. Express-session is further incorporated for handling sessions and cookies.

Fig 4. Framework of social media challenges for marketing managers.

Fig 3. Social Intranet Methodology.

Fig 5. Social Media Marketing Methodology(SMM).

IV. RESULT

The social media website ArtSocials is deployed and fully functional. As of now, the target is to attract an audience of artistic caliber towards this platform.

V. CONCLUSION

We believe that a platform such as this, an online platform free to use and accessible by anyone anywhere will give a boost to artistic talent. There are many social media websites that are popular and used by people all over the world like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Youtube, TikTok, Reddit, Pinterest etc. However, in all these platforms there are all sorts of people including politicians, businessmen, army men, etc., with all sorts of interests and all sorts of activities going on including cooking, education, memes, etc. Hence, if there is a social media that is artist-centric, artists can grow together and build a community of their own, allowing talents to nurture and evolve in public and perhaps start to earn from their art.

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